

FLEXDIS

Deliverable 1.1

Steady-state Models of Distribution Grids for Voltage Stability Evaluation

Document information

Deliverable nr	D1.1
Deliverable Name	Steady-state Models of Distribution Grids for Voltage Stability
Release date	08/08/2025
Dissemination level	Public
Status	Submitted
Authors	Alex Blanco Castro, Josep Fanals (eRoots Analytics), Hessam Golmohamadi, Birgitte Bak-Jensen (AAU) and Marc Cheah-Mane (UPC)

Document history:

Version	Date of issue	Content and changes	Edited by
1	08/08/2025	Full deliverable	Alex Blanco Castro
2	19/09/2025	Additions	Alex Blanco Castro and Hessam Golmohamadi
3	23/09/2025	Review	Marc Cheah-Mane
4	24/09/2025	Review	Birgitte Bak-Jensen
5	06/11/2025	Final version	Marc Cheah-Mane

Deliverable beneficiaries:

WP and Task
WP1- Impact analysis of distributed renewable generation
Task 1.2 – Steady state and short-circuit analysis for voltage stability

Table of contents

1 Introduction	8
1.1 Conventional steady-state analysis	8
1.2 Steady-state analysis for short-circuit calculations	9
1.3 Steady-state analysis for unbalanced systems	9
1.4 Objectives	10
1.5 Outline	11
2 Balanced Steady State Analysis	12
2.1 Analysis framework	12
2.2 Intelligent Control of Flexibility Assets	13
2.3 Danish Demonstration Site: Hyllegaard Høje	15
2.3.1 LV Power Network Model	16
2.3.2 Thermonet System	17
2.3.3 Integration of Flexibility Assets into LV Network	18
2.3.4 CEMS-Based Control Architecture	19
2.3.5 Aggregation of Flexibility to MV Network	19
3 Unbalanced models for steady state analysis	21
3.1 Overhead Lines	22
3.1.1 π model	22
3.1.2 Carson series impedance	23
3.1.3 Example results	25
3.1.4 Shunt admittance	26
3.1.5 Kron's reduction	26
3.2 Transformers	27
3.2.1 Delta-star (Dy) connection	30
3.3 Loads	32
3.3.1 Impedance (Z) definition	33
3.3.2 Current (I) definition	33
3.3.3 Power (P) definition	34
3.4 Generators	34
3.5 Voltage Source Converters	36
4 Validation of unbalanced models	39
4.1 IEEE 13 Node Test Feeder	39
4.2 IEEE European Low Voltage Test Feeder	46
4.3 Single Line-to-Ground Fault (SLG)	48

4.4 Line-to-Line Fault (LL)	51
4.5 Double Line-to-Ground Fault (DLG)	53
4.6 Three-Phase Fault (LLL)	55
4.7 Three-Phase-to-Ground Fault (LLLG)	57
5 Conclusions	59

List of Figures

1	Diagram of a part of distribution grid built-up in DIgSILENT with active demands like EVs, heat pumps and PVs	12
2	Steady state analysis in distribution grid in DIgSILENT with results for line loading, transformer loading and nodal voltage	14
3	Distributed control and operation of flexible loads in a power distribution network in DIgSILENT	15
4	Model of LV power grids in Hyllegaard Høje built up in PowerFactory	16
5	A sample of color coding to indicate voltage levels of power nodes and loading levels of lines and cables in steady-state analysis	17
6	Map of the network in Hyllegaard Høje	17
7	Integration of EVs and heat pumps into local LV network in Hyllegaard Høje for flexibility assessment	18
8	Electrical power system network	21
9	Line π equivalent circuit	22
10	Carson's geometry data of the tower configuration	24
11	Example of a power line geometric arrangement	25
12	Two-winding transformer	28
13	Single-phase transformer equivalent electrical circuit	28
14	Zig-zag transformer connection	30
15	Delta - star connection	30
16	Schematic ZIP load model	32
17	Star-connected load (left) and delta-connected load (right) representations	33
18	Thévenin equivalent circuit scheme	35
19	Norton equivalent circuit scheme	36
20	Representation of a VSC	36
21	IEEE 13 Node Test Feeder representation	39
22	Voltage magnitude per bus in phase a	42
23	Voltage angle per bus in phase a	43
24	Voltage magnitude per bus in phase b	44
25	Voltage angle per bus in phase b	44
26	Voltage magnitude per bus in phase c	45
27	Voltage angle per bus in phase c	46
28	Single-line diagram of the European Low Voltage Test Feeder	47
29	Phase c voltage profile comparison for hour 14	48
30	Phase b voltage profile comparison for hour 5	48
31	Phase-to-ground short-circuit at the bus 634 of the IEEE 13 Node Test Feeder	49

32	Single Line-to-Ground Fault (SLG)	49
33	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a SLG fault	50
34	Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase b during a SLG fault	50
35	Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase c during a SLG fault	50
36	Line-to-Line Fault (LL)	51
37	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a LL fault	52
38	Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase b during a LL fault	52
39	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a LL fault	52
40	Double Line-to-Ground Fault (DLG)	53
41	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a DLG fault	54
42	Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase b during a DLG fault	54
43	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a DLG fault	54
44	Three-Phase Fault (LLL)	55
45	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a LLL fault	56
46	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase b during a LLL fault	56
47	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a LLL fault	56
48	Three-Phase-to-Ground Fault (LLLG)	57
49	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a LLLG fault	58
50	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase b during a LLLG fault	58
51	Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a LLLG fault	58

List of Tables

1	Non-exhaustive list of control combinations for a VSC under balanced conditions	37
2	Transformer data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case	40
3	Load data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case	40
4	Line data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case	41
5	Capacitor bank data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case	41
6	Phase a Voltage Profile of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case	42
7	Phase b Voltage Profile of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case	43
8	Phase c Voltage Profile of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case	45

1 Introduction

1.1 Conventional steady-state analysis

Steady state analysis in distribution grids is a set of calculations in unchanged (normal) conditions where the dynamic transients of the electrical equipment died out and the system works in a constant manner. Therefore, it makes it possible for the power system operator to check the technical status of the power grid equipment, e.g., power generators, demands, overhead lines, underground cables or transformers.

Generally, in steady state analysis, the following variables are calculated:

- Voltage magnitude and angles at all buses of the distribution grid.
- Active and reactive power flows in branches (lines, cables or transformers).
- Overloading of these branches (based on apparent powers or currents) and over/under voltage of buses.

Therefore, by calculation of the above-mentioned variables, the Distribution System Operator (DSO) can identify key technical issues of the power grids, including:

- Voltage violation: under-voltage and over-voltage of power nodes, which can affect the lifespan of power equipment, damage critical demands or lead to misoperation of equipment (in case of under-voltages).
- Reactive power imbalance: detection of nodes with deficit/excess of reactive power which causes voltage instability and lower the total grid efficiency.
- Overloading: identification of overloading of transformers and lines that affects the safe operation of the distribution grids.
- Hosting capacity limits: calculation of hosting capacity of renewables, e.g., PV and wind, in the distribution grids without violation of voltage or thermal limits. Also, this can be related to hosting capacity for the electrification of transportation and heating, e.g. with Electric Vehicles (EV) and heat-pumps.
- Power loss: quantification of power loss in different parts of the distribution grids that can be used further for energy efficiency improvement measures.
- Grid reinforcement and reconfiguration: identify weak lines or nodes where further reinforcement or reconfiguration are required to keep the system's stability and reliability.

1.2 Steady-state analysis for short-circuit calculations

Steady state analysis for short-circuit calculations is motivated by the rapidly evolving nature of modern power systems, which are increasingly dominated by power electronics converters rather than conventional synchronous generators. The deployment of converters for renewable grid integration, energy storage, HVDC transmission, and other applications fundamentally changes system behavior during faults, requiring new approaches for reliable short-circuit assessment.

In particular, converters feature fast dynamic responses and full controllability under disturbances, but they are also subject to current saturation during fault events, which alters their contribution to fault currents. Traditional short-circuit calculation methods, typically based on linear models and the use of Thevenin equivalents for synchronous generators, are not capable of capturing the nonlinear behavior, control modes, and current-limited operation of converters. Standards such as IEC 60909 recommend modeling converters as current sources with maximum injection capability, yet do not address how to determine the current angle or incorporate specific control modes during fault scenarios [1]. Steady state short-circuit analysis encompasses the control and saturation behavior of converters without requiring detailed dynamic models, which enables more accurate and efficient assessment of system responses during faults. This kind of analysis is essential for proper equipment sizing, tuning protection systems, and optimizing the grid-support functions expected of converters in the context of grid codes. Furthermore, while dynamic simulations remain a valuable reference for accuracy, they are computationally expensive and time-consuming, rendering steady state approaches preferable for large-scale or routine studies. By explicitly including the steady-state control equations governing each converter and their saturation states, steady state analysis enables the identification of realistic fault equilibrium points, thus providing results that are more closely aligned with how modern, converter-rich power systems behave in practice [2].

1.3 Steady-state analysis for unbalanced systems

The transmission and distribution of electrical energy in alternating current (AC) form has historically favoured the use of three-phase systems due to their superior efficiency, power handling capability, and infrastructure compatibility. In ideal conditions, these systems are perfectly balanced, with each phase carrying identical sinusoidal waveforms equally spaced by 120 electrical degrees. Under such assumptions, the network impedance is symmetrical, and positive-sequence modelling suffices for most steady-state analyses.

However, real-world power systems are rarely perfectly balanced. Several factors, such as untransposed transmission lines, uneven distribution of loads, single-phase connections

to distribution feeders or unbalanced faults, introduce asymmetries in both voltage and current. The increasing prevalence of converter-based distributed energy resources and single-phase consumer electronics exacerbates this phenomenon, especially in low-voltage networks. In these situations, classical analysis, relying on the method of symmetrical components, can struggle to accurately represent the system's true behaviour.

The method of symmetrical components, based on Fortescue's theorem, provides an elegant mathematical abstraction that simplifies the analysis of asymmetrical faults by decoupling the system under linear conditions. It has been widely used for classical analysis and protection studies, and is highly efficient for practical cases. Nevertheless, it is limited in its ability to represent complex unbalances, particularly when the coupling between sequences is strong or when the system is inherently nonlinear. This method assumes linearity, is less practical for time-domain simulations, and requires careful handling of zero and negative sequence paths. Furthermore, difficulties can arise in the assembly of sequence networks and the solution of sequence equivalents, especially in complex or non-radially structured systems involving significant transformer interactions [3].

Consequently, direct phase-domain (abc) modelling and solution methods have gained prominence, as they allow for a more granular and accurate representation of the system's physical behaviour. The phase coordinate method uses direct phase variables, offering high ease of physical interpretation as it corresponds directly to physical quantities. This approach naturally incorporates asymmetry, handles nonlinearities well, and scales naturally to multi-phase systems, making it preferred for transients and time-domain simulations, as well as for EMTP-type tools and control design. It simplifies the analysis of multiple unbalanced faults on unbalanced systems, also during simultaneous fault conditions [4]. Finally, it also enables the analysis of systems with any number of phases, not just three, making it suitable for all types of networks, from large power plants, through transmission and distribution systems, to our homes.

1.4 Objectives

This *Deliverable D1.1 - Steady-state Models of Distribution Grids for Voltage Stability* forms part of the FLEXDIS project, which aims to develop flexible digital solutions for the operation and planning of distribution networks, supporting their transition towards more sustainable and resilient systems.

AAU has made a balanced steady-state analysis of the operation of the distribution grids to identify voltage stability issues, hosting capacity limits, and reinforcement needs. The developed models in DIGSILENT PowerFactory integrates flexible assets like EVs, heat pumps, PVs, and batteries. Furthermore, it designs intelligent controllers and community energy management systems (CEMS) to unlock flexibility and enhance grid reliability, while

demonstrating the approach at the Danish Hyllegaard Høje site.

eRoots Analytics aims to implement accurate models for the simulation and analysis of three-phase unbalanced power systems in steady state, moving beyond the limitations of sequence-based approaches. This unbalanced power system formulation is implemented as part of the Python-based and open-source power system simulation tool VeraGrid [5]. The specific objectives of this work are:

- To create a device library with unbalanced models for key system elements such as overhead lines, transformers, loads, generators and reactive power compensation equipment. Special attention will be paid to power converters, which present significant challenges due to the complex mapping of their dynamic response and operational limits, such as current saturation into the steady-state domain during unbalanced fault conditions.
- To formulate and implement a three-phase power flow solver that operates directly in the phase reference frame. The tool should be validated with different challenging test networks due to its wide range of asymmetry types.
- To extend the short-circuit calculation capabilities in VeraGrid to accurately simulate asymmetrical faults, outgrowing the classical method of the sequence abstraction and directly obtaining the real electrical quantities.

1.5 Outline

The structure of this deliverable is as follows:

- Chapter 2 analyses balanced distribution grids, focusing on voltage stability and the role of flexibility assets.
- Chapter 3 describes the mathematical models used to represent three-phase elements in the network.
- Chapter 4 presents the three-phase power flow and short-circuit calculation results, simulating unbalanced test feeders and asymmetrical faults directly in the phase domain.
- Finally, Chapter 5 summaries the key contributions and discusses potential directions for future work.

2 Balanced Steady State Analysis

2.1 Analysis framework

In order to perform the steady state analysis of balanced systems, Power Factory DIgSILENT is employed. This software makes possible building a model of the power distribution grid and represent different types of generation, e.g., thermal and renewable, and demand, including electrical, heat and mobility. Therefore, active demands including heat pumps, EVs and battery storage are modelled in different points of connections (POC) of the distribution grid. The active demands can provide flexibility for the upstream grid in response to voltage variations (under/over voltage issues). They can also contribute to balancing transformers overloading and relieving power congestion of weak lines. In DIgSILENT, technical controllers are designed to unlock flexibility of the active demands.

Figure 1 shows a diagram of a distribution grid in DIgSILENT PowerFactory with flexibility assets connected to different nodes.

Figure 1: Diagram of a part of distribution grid built-up in DIgSILENT with active demands like EVs, heat pumps and PVs

In order to perform a voltage stability analysis, the following steps are taken:

- **Data Collection:** input data of the distribution grid is collected from our industrial partner. This data includes configuration of the distribution grid, characteristics of power lines, cables, transformers, e.g., length, capacity, nominal voltage, thermal limits, etc.
- **Network build-up:** based on technical data, the distribution network is built up in the DIgSILENT PowerFactory. In addition, the demand and local DGs of the grids are connected.
- **Load flow analysis:** load flow calculations are the main tool for steady state analysis. It is normally done by Newton-Raphson method and quasi-dynamic analysis within the software. This step forms the foundation for identifying potential voltage issues.
- **Voltage stability assessment:** Based on the results of the load flow analysis, voltage stability is evaluated. The assessment includes voltage profiles under normal and stressed operating conditions to identify weak nodes with high sensitivity to load changes, and to determine the proximity of the system to voltage collapse. In this way, some tools such as PV curves, QV analysis, and Jacobian singularity checks are used.
- **Voltage compensation:** after detection of weak nodes, with under-/over-voltage problems, control mechanisms are designed to regulate voltage variations. The control mechanisms unlock flexibility potential through demand-side management. Flexibility assets like heat pumps, EV chargers, electrical storage and PV generators are used for flexibility provision.

Figure 2 shows results of the steady state analysis performed for the distribution grid. In this figure, the daily profile of transformer loading, line loading and nodal voltage are explained.

2.2 Intelligent Control of Flexibility Assets

Power Factory DIgSILENT makes it possible to design intelligent controller for flexibility assets like heat pumps and EVs. This is done by DPL (DIgSILENT Programming Language) and DSL (DIgSILENT Simulation Language). The designed controllers unleash the energy flexibility in response to an external signal. The external signal can be a local variable of the distribution grid, e.g., voltage fluctuations, transformer overloading and power congestion, or global variable, e.g., supply-demand balance. In the former, the local variables are extracted from the installed meters on local nodes of the grid. In the latter, by considering

Figure 2: Steady state analysis in distribution grid in DIgSILENT with results for line loading, transformer loading and nodal voltage

a correlation between electricity prices and renewable power availability in the bulk power grid, electricity prices will be considered as a strong signal of renewable power availability. Therefore, price-responsive controllers can unlock demand flexibility in response to renewable power availability in the supply side.

Regarding the intelligent control mechanism, three types of energy flexibility will be studied including power, heat-to-power and mobility-to-power flexibility.

- **Power Flexibility:** flexibility potentials of electrical storage, PV generation systems, e.g., roof-top or balcony PV, and residential buildings.
- **Heat-to-Power Flexibility:** heat pumps are the main source for this type of flexibility. The electrical compressor of heat pumps can be turned off/on (down/up) very quickly in response to a demand response request. Since the thermal dynamics of buildings have a slower time constant than electrical systems, heat pumps can serve as a substantial source of demand flexibility without compromising the thermal comfort of residents.
- **Mobility-to-Power Flexibility:** charging points of EVs are the main source of mobility-to-power flexibility. EV chargers, including residential and commercial points, can provide energy flexibility in two modes including vehicle-to-grid (V2G) and grid-to-vehicle (G2V). In both modes, intelligent controllers are required to optimize the charging and discharging operations of the EVs in response to the grid signals. Intelligent controllers

are connected to the chargers and EVs through manufacturers’ API.

Figure 3 describes flowchart of intelligent controllers for EVs, heat pumps and batteries in DIgSILENT to unlock flexibility in response to local grid signals. In this diagram, different control schemes are designed, e.g., droop controller for EVs and on/off controller for the heat pumps.

Figure 3: Distributed control and operation of flexible loads in a power distribution network in DIgSILENT

2.3 Danish Demonstration Site: Hyllegaard Høje

The Danish demo site is located in Hyllegaard Høje, where AAU and Neogrid are collaborating on a residential energy flexibility testbed. The setup includes 13 residential buildings (clusters of 3–5 households) connected via a shared low-temperature thermal grid known as Thermonet. Each building is equipped with a heat pump, and the full site is monitored and controlled through a community energy management system (CEMS) developed by Neogrid.

The demonstration integrates several distributed energy resources (DERs): rooftop PV systems (24.6 kW total), residential EV chargers (three stations), indoor climate sensors, and soon-to-be-added battery energy storage units. Residential electricity demand and heating loads are modelled in coordination with local grid operations. The energy flexibility available at the site includes:

- PV and battery-based flexibility for local power generation.
- EV charging flexibility (mobility-to-power).
- Power-to-heat flexibility, enabled through building-level heat pumps and the Thermonet system.

To analyse the system dynamics and flexibility potentials, two models are developed:

- A LV power distribution network model, built in DIgSILENT PowerFactory.
- A thermal system model, representing the Thermonet configuration.

2.3.1 LV Power Network Model

The local grid model simulates the full low-voltage electricity distribution system in PowerFactory, capturing the integration of renewables and flexible loads. The site is fed through two 0.63 MVA transformers (IDs 41542 and 41543) and operates as a radial feeder network. Lumped loads are used to represent combined household and heat pump consumption at each node. PV generation, EV charging, and future battery units are connected at defined points of common coupling (PCCs).

Figure 4 shows the network model layout. Load flow simulations are performed to assess transformer and cable loading, voltage levels, and hosting capacity under different flexibility scenarios. Color coding in Figure 5 reflects operational stresses (e.g., overvoltage or transformer overload) under peak and flexible conditions.

Figure 4: Model of LV power grids in Hyllegaard Høje built up in PowerFactory

Lower Limit of Allowed Voltage:			Max. Loading of Edge Element:		
Lower Voltage ... p.u.	Colour		Loading Range %	Colour	
<= 1.	Green		>= 80.	Orange	
<= 0.95	Cyan		>= 100.	Red	
<= 0.9	Blue				

Figure 5: A sample of color coding to indicate voltage levels of power nodes and loading levels of lines and cables in steady-state analysis

2.3.2 Thermonet System

The thermonet at Hyllegaard Høje is a shared, low-temperature district heating system tailored for compact residential developments. It consists of approximately 30 km of uninsulated piping looped underground, circulating ambient-temperature water. Each building has a small heat pump that upgrades the temperature for space heating and domestic hot water.

This design addresses issues commonly seen with individual air-to-water heat pumps, such as noise problems, and avoids the cost and spatial demands of separate ground-source heat pumps. Thermonet centralizes the underground infrastructure, making it more cost-efficient while reducing thermal interference risks.

The Thermonet concept aligns with integrated energy management. It enables dynamic operation of heat pumps based on electricity market signals and DSO flexibility requests. This makes it possible to unlock significant power-to-heat flexibility without compromising end-user comfort. Figure 6 shows a diagram of Thermonet in Hyllegaard Høje demo site.

Figure 6: Map of thermonet in Hyllegaard Høje

2.3.3 Integration of Flexibility Assets into LV Network

To simulate and analyze the interplay of DERs and flexibility services, all energy assets, i.e., heat pumps, PVs, EVs, and batteries, are embedded in the LV grid model. Technical specifications for each asset are used to place and configure their connections accurately within the PowerFactory environment. Residential demand is modeled accordingly.

Heat pumps, which are boosted by the Thermonet’s ambient loop, are key to unlocking flexibility. Their operation depends on both thermal demand and available electrical capacity. The interaction between the Thermonet and the local grid determines how much demand can be shifted without violating technical limits, e.g., voltage drops or transformer overloading. Therefore, the information about booster heat pumps and heat demands are extracted from the thermonet map and integrated into the LV network.

After the integration of flexibility assets into the LV network, intelligent local controllers are being developed in DIgSILENT using DSL and DPL to manage asset-level behavior. These controllers are implemented in the simulation environment and interfaced with the grid model to test response to dynamic conditions and external signals. These controllers optimize the operations of responsive demand, such as EVs and heat pumps, in response to technical problems of the local grid, like undervoltage and transformer overloading, or dynamic electricity prices. Figure 7 shows part of the local network with EV chargers and heat pumps mapped to specific nodes.

Figure 7: Integration of EVs and heat pumps into local LV network in Hyllegaard Høje for flexibility assessment

2.3.4 CEMS-Based Control Architecture

Neogrid leads the development of the CEMS for this site. The system integrates forecasting, optimization, and real-time control features aimed at improving the operational efficiency of the local energy community. Its main functionalities include:

- Dynamic control of heat pumps in response to real-time electricity prices.
- Predictive scheduling to align PV generation with heating needs.
- Automated load shifting based on grid constraints, e.g., transformer loading, voltage profiles.
- User interfaces to provide household-level feedback on cost savings, carbon impact, and consumption profiles.

The CEMS is tested in two living lab configurations: one community-scale and one compact centralized setup. Both demonstrate scalability and adaptability to diverse residential configurations. The expected outcomes are as follows:

- Reduction in household electricity costs.
- Improved voltage stability through demand response.
- Increased local energy autonomy and use of renewables.
- Enhanced user engagement due to visibility and control of energy flows.

2.3.5 Aggregation of Flexibility to MV Network

In order to study the impacts of energy flexibility on higher voltage levels, the local LV model of Hyllegaard Høje will be aggregated to the 50 kV network developed by Chalmers University of Technology. In this way, the flexibility potentials of assets like heat pumps, EVs and PVs are studied in the MV network. To enable the aggregation model, the following steps are suggested:

- Net power profiling: the LV network is connected to the higher voltage level through 0.63 MVA transformers. The net load and generation of the LV network are determined to give a time-varying profile of active (P) and reactive power (Q) seen by the MV network.
- Time-series exporting: after the determination of a P and Q, these are exported to the MV network as time series data in appropriate time resolution, e.g., 15-minutes or hourly basis. In this step, the time series includes base scenarios and different flexibility-activated scenarios for heat pumps, EVs and PVs.

- Flexibility scenarios scaling: then the flexibility-activated scenarios can be scaled up to simulate a larger area (than the baseline scenario) that can be connected to the MV network. In the base scenario, 13 residential buildings are modeled. In the scaling scenarios, extra residential buildings are considered with different diversity factors, simultaneity factors, and penetration levels of DERs. Therefore, it will be studied how the combined similar communities impact the operation of the MV grid.

3 Unbalanced models for steady state analysis

The conventional elements of the electrical power system are generators, loads, transformers, and lines, as well as the necessary reactive power compensation equipment. These elements are suitably interconnected to enable the generation, transportation, and consumption of electricity to meet system demand at any given point in time [6]. Traditionally, the electrical power network has been then divided into generation, transmission, distribution, and consumer subsystems, as represented in Figure 8. Transmission networks operate at high voltages (HV) to minimise transport losses. Conversely, electricity is generated at medium voltages (MV), and step-up transformers are employed at the generator substation to raise the voltage to transmission levels. In contrast, step-down transformers are used to reduce the high transmission voltages to levels suitable for distribution (MV), and eventually for industrial, commercial, and residential applications at low voltages (LV) [7].

Figure 8: Electrical power system network

Three-phase synchronous generators has been used as the main source to produce electrical power, which is delivered to demand points via alternating current (AC) three-phase transmission and distribution lines. The geometrical arrangement of these lines introduces some impedance unbalance between phases. Often, long-distance transmission circuits consist of more than one three-phase circuit and include series and shunt compensation to enable stable operation [8]. It should also be noted that the windings of three-phase transformers can be connected in various ways to suit specific requirements, and that transformer connections must be modelled in detail when system imbalances cannot be neglected in power system studies [9]. Additionally, distribution load points may be highly unbalanced due to the prevalence of individual single-phase loads. An increasing share of photovoltaic (PV) generation is now connected at the LV level, with part of this output is directly consumed there or injected into distribution.

The application tool used to assess the steady-state operation of power systems exhibiting a considerable degree of unbalance is known as three-phase power flow [10]. In this application, all operations are carried out on a per-phase basis, and all power system components are modelled in the phase reference frame [11]. This project considers that the system's geometrical unbalances are significant and that the system load is unbalanced. Therefore, all power system components will be represented in the phase domain.

3.1 Overhead Lines

Power lines are fundamental components of power systems, responsible for transmitting electrical energy from generation sources to loads. They consist of a group of phase conductors located at a finite distance from the earth's surface and may use the ground as a return path. Accordingly, it becomes necessary to account for this effect when calculating the line parameters [12]. High-voltage transmission lines may contain several conductors per phase (known as bundled conductors) and ground wires, while distribution lines may include a neutral wire as a return path. Both transmission and distribution circuits may introduce considerable geometric unbalances, hence electrical unbalances, depending on their layout [13]. The main objective is to develop an overhead power line model that enables precise calculation of voltage drops and losses during the power transmission process. The basis of power line modelling is to determine the resistance R , inductance L , conductance G , and capacitance C per unit length [14].

3.1.1 π model

Lines can be represented using mathematical models that describe their electrical behaviour. It is a current practice to model the inductive and resistive effects of multi-conductor transmission lines as a series impedance matrix, and the capacitive effects as a shunt admittance matrix. The overall transmission line model then can be represented by the π equivalent model, as shown in Figure 9. It consists of:

- Series impedance: $\vec{Z}_{series} = R + jX$
- Shunt admittance: $\vec{Y}_{shunt} = G + jB$

Where R is the series equivalent resistance of the conductors, X is the series self and mutual inductive reactances resulting from the magnetic fields surrounding the conductors, G is the shunt conductance and B represents the shunt susceptance derived from the line capacitance due to the induced electric fields.

Figure 9: Line π equivalent circuit

The line capacitance is split between the two connection points with the resistance and the reactance in the middle, whose shape gives the so-called π -model. Although this single-phase simplification is a widely used technique, when modeling unbalanced systems it is needed to consider a general 5-wire approach, that later becomes a 3-wire equivalent. This 5-wire model is that including the three phases, the neutral and the ground:

- The first three wires are the three-phase abc conductors. These carry the alternating current (AC) electricity and are used to distribute power efficiently.
- The fourth wire is the neutral conductor n . It provides a return path for unbalanced current and is often grounded at substations to stabilize the system voltage.
- The fifth wire is typically a ground wire g , which is connected to earth to protect equipment and people by providing a low-resistance path for fault currents, ensuring safety and system stability. It is also known as the shield wire.

Not all physical lines will have neutral, and the "ground return" is certainly not a wire, but it is represented as one in order to close the electrical circuit. Each wire has its own impedance, however, other impedances arise from the electromagnetic coupling of the wires, such that it is necessary to use a 5×5 matrix to represent the total line impedance or admittance.

$$\vec{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Z}_{aa} & \vec{Z}_{ab} & \vec{Z}_{ac} & \vec{Z}_{an} & \vec{Z}_{ag} \\ \vec{Z}_{ba} & \vec{Z}_{bb} & \vec{Z}_{bc} & \vec{Z}_{bn} & \vec{Z}_{bg} \\ \vec{Z}_{ca} & \vec{Z}_{cb} & \vec{Z}_{cc} & \vec{Z}_{cn} & \vec{Z}_{cg} \\ \vec{Z}_{na} & \vec{Z}_{nb} & \vec{Z}_{nc} & \vec{Z}_{nn} & \vec{Z}_{ng} \\ \vec{Z}_{ga} & \vec{Z}_{gb} & \vec{Z}_{gc} & \vec{Z}_{gn} & \vec{Z}_{gg} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Most transmission power lines do not carry the neutral, since that one is normally earthed at both ends of the line. Also, the ground return effect can be incorporated into the phase impedance as it will be detailed later. Then, it can be simply expressed as a 3×3 matrix:

$$\vec{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Z}_{aa} & \vec{Z}_{ab} & \vec{Z}_{ac} \\ \vec{Z}_{ba} & \vec{Z}_{bb} & \vec{Z}_{bc} \\ \vec{Z}_{ca} & \vec{Z}_{cb} & \vec{Z}_{cc} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

3.1.2 Carson series impedance

Carson's equations are used in power system analysis to calculate the series self and mutual impedances of overhead transmission lines, taking into account the effects of the ground return path [15]. They are based on the following assumptions:

- The conductors are perfectly horizontal above ground and are long enough so that three-dimensional end effects can be neglected. This makes the field problem two-dimensional. The sag is taken into account indirectly by using an average height above ground.
- The free space is homogeneous and lossless, with permeability μ_0 and permittivity ε_0 .
- The earth is homogeneous, with uniform resistivity ρ , permeability μ_0 , and permittivity ε_0 , bounded by a flat plane of infinite extent.
- The spacing between conductors is at least one order of magnitude larger than the conductor radius, so that proximity effects can be ignored.

Figure 10: Carson's geometry data of the tower configuration

The elements of the series impedance matrix can then be calculated from the geometry of the tower configuration (see Figure 10) and from characteristics of the conductors. The self and mutual impedances can be computed using equations (3) and (4) respectively [16].

$$\vec{Z}_{ii} = (R_i + R_{ii}^c) + j \left(\omega \frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} \ln \frac{2h_i}{r_i} + X_i + X_{ii}^c \right) \quad (3)$$

$$\vec{Z}_{ij} = \vec{Z}_{ji} = R_{ij}^c + j \left(\omega \frac{\mu_0}{2\pi} \ln \frac{D_{ij}}{d_{ij}} + X_{ij}^c \right) \quad (4)$$

Where:

- R_i and X_i are the internal resistance and reactance of conductor i in Ω/km .
- R^c and X^c are the Carson's correction terms for earth return effects in Ω/km .
- $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the angular frequency in rad/s.
- h_i is the average height above ground of conductor i in m.
- r_i is the radius of conductor i in m.
- d_{ij} is the distance between conductors i and j in m.
- D_{ij} is the distance between conductor i and the image of conductor j in m.

3.1.3 Example results

Carson's exact formulation for calculating the series impedance of overhead lines has been implemented and validated. To verify its correctness, a three-phase transmission line is analysed.

The line operates at 50 Hz, with an earth resistivity of $100 \Omega \cdot \text{m}$. Each phase consists of a single conductor with a radius of 10.5 mm and an internal resistance of $0.1363 \Omega/\text{km}$. The geometric configuration of the conductors is illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Example of a power line geometric arrangement

The computed series impedance values using Carson's method are shown in equation (5). These results have been cross-validated using PowerFactory [17], confirming the accuracy of the implementation. Carson's formulation has therefore been adopted for use in VeraGrid to ensure precision in modelling and simulation.

$$\vec{Z}_{\text{Carson}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.1826 + 0.7304j & 0.0462 + 0.2733j & 0.0462 + 0.2298j \\ 0.0463 + 0.2733j & 0.1826 + 0.7304j & 0.0462 + 0.2733j \\ 0.0462 + 0.2298j & 0.0463 + 0.2733j & 0.1826 + 0.7304j \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

3.1.4 Shunt admittance

Just as the calculation of the series impedance has accounted for the resistance and inductance, the shunt admittance must incorporate the capacitance between the conductor and the ground, as well as between conductors, as previously explained. These effects can be mathematically modelled using the equations developed in [16], given that the air is lossless, the earth is uniformly at zero potential and the conductor radius is at least an order of magnitude smaller than the distance among the conductors, which it is reasonable for overhead lines. Therefore, the shunt admittance between a conductor and the ground can be obtained using equation (6), whereas the shunt admittance between two conductors should be calculated via equation (7).

$$\vec{Y}_{ii} = j \frac{\omega}{2\pi\epsilon_0} \ln \frac{2h_i}{r_i} \quad (6)$$

$$\vec{Y}_{ij} = j \frac{\omega}{2\pi\epsilon_0} \ln \frac{D_{ij}}{d_{ij}} \quad (7)$$

Where $\epsilon_0 = \frac{1}{\mu_0 c^2} \approx 8,85 \cdot 10^{-12}$ F/m is the free space permittivity.

3.1.5 Kron's reduction

Kron's reduction, or node elimination, is a technique from network theory used to simplify a multi-node electrical network by eliminating certain nodes, often called internal or passive nodes, while preserving the electrical behaviour at the remaining nodes.

Assuming a set of nodes divided into two groups between ground conductors g (to eliminate) and phase conductors p (to keep), the impedance matrix is partitioned accordingly:

$$\vec{Z} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Z}_{gg} & \vec{Z}_{gp} \\ \vec{Z}_{pg} & \vec{Z}_{pp} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Where:

- \vec{Z}_{gg} is the impedance between eliminated nodes.
- \vec{Z}_{gp} is the mutual impedance between eliminated and preserved nodes.
- \vec{Z}_{pg} is the mutual impedance between preserved and eliminated nodes.
- \vec{Z}_{pp} is the impedance between preserved nodes.

Then, the network equations are:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{U}_g \\ \vec{U}_p \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Z}_{gg} & \vec{Z}_{gp} \\ \vec{Z}_{pg} & \vec{Z}_{pp} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_g \\ \vec{I}_p \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Assuming that the eliminated nodes are held at zero voltage because they are grounded, $\vec{U}_g = 0$. From the first row of the system:

$$\vec{I}_e = -\vec{Z}_{gg}^{-1} \cdot \vec{Z}_{gp} \cdot \vec{I}_p \quad (10)$$

Then, substituting \vec{I}_e in the second row:

$$\vec{U}_p = (\vec{Z}_{pp} - \vec{Z}_{pg} \cdot \vec{Z}_{gg}^{-1} \cdot \vec{Z}_{gp}) \vec{I}_p \quad (11)$$

Finally, the Kron-reduced impedance matrix is defined as:

$$\vec{Z}_{\text{Kron}} = \vec{Z}_{pp} - \vec{Z}_{pg} \cdot \vec{Z}_{gg}^{-1} \cdot \vec{Z}_{gp} \quad (12)$$

This new matrix allows to describe the electrical behaviour of the remaining phase nodes p , while implicitly incorporating the effect of the eliminated ground nodes g , which were assumed to be held at 0 V.

3.2 Transformers

Power transformers are essential components of the power system. In general, they provide an interface between sections of the network that operate at different rated voltages, for example, between a generating plant and the transmission network [18]. In this section, two-winding, three-phase transformers will be modelled. Therefore, it is convenient to treat the electric circuit, formed by the copper windings, separately from the magnetic circuit, formed by the iron core [19]. The winding impedance \vec{Z}_s is obtained from a short-circuit test, whereas the iron-core shunt admittance \vec{Y}_{sh} is determined from open-circuit tests.

The starting point for developing comprehensive steady-state transformer models [20] is the schematic representation of the basic two-winding transformer shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Two-winding transformer

The two transformer windings, termed the primary and secondary, contain N_p and N_s turns, respectively [21]. The voltages and currents in both windings are related by a matrix of short-circuit and open-circuit admittance parameters, represented in the electrical equivalent circuit of Figure 13 and given in (13).

Figure 13: Single-phase transformer equivalent electrical circuit

Representing the transformer parameters in the per-unit system, it converts the original voltage ratio $N_p : N_s$ into a unity ratio of $1 : 1$. Power transformers are, however, often fitted with a tap-changing mechanism that permits a degree of voltage regulation at one of their terminals [22]. This regulation is achieved by injecting a small variable voltage of magnitude and phase into the ratio $m : 1$. Figure 13 also includes the tap transformers m_f and m_t in the branch's π model, as in the previous section on power lines. These virtual tap transformers arise solely from the per-unit normalisation of the voltages, as they reconcile the nominal voltage of a device at a connection point with the nominal voltage of the point itself.

Then, based on the single-phase transformer model shown in Figure 13, the corresponding primitive admittance matrix is derived and presented in equation (13), which relates the primary and secondary voltages and currents.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_p \\ \vec{I}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m^2 m_f^2} & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m}^* m_f m_t} \\ \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m} m_t m_f} & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m_t^2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{U}_p \\ \vec{U}_s \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

Using nodal analysis, general models for multi-winding and multi-phase transformers can be derived [23]. The essence of the method is to transform the single-phase voltages and currents at each winding, denoted "123456", into the "ABCabc" phase reference frame, where consecutive numbers refer to the primary and secondary windings of each phase (e.g., 1 and 2 correspond to phase *Aa*). The primitive parameters of three identical single-phase transformers are arranged as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_1 \\ \vec{I}_2 \\ \vec{I}_3 \\ \vec{I}_4 \\ \vec{I}_5 \\ \vec{I}_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m^2 m_f^2} & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m}^* m_f m_t} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m} m_t m_f} & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m_t^2} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m^2 m_f^2} & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m}^* m_f m_t} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m} m_t m_f} & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m_t^2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m^2 m_f^2} & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m}^* m_f m_t} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\vec{m} m_t m_f} & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m_t^2} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{U}_1 \\ \vec{U}_2 \\ \vec{U}_3 \\ \vec{U}_4 \\ \vec{U}_5 \\ \vec{U}_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

Expressed in compact form, the resulting expression is:

$$\vec{I}_{\text{coils}} = \vec{Y}_{\text{primitive}} \cdot \vec{U}_{\text{coils}} \quad (15)$$

Which can be operated in order to relate phase magnitudes:

$$\vec{I}_{\text{phases}} = C_I^{-1} \cdot \vec{Y}_{\text{primitive}} \cdot C_U \cdot \vec{U}_{\text{phases}} \quad (16)$$

It follows that the next step is to find the connectivity matrices C_U and C_I , which relate the voltages and currents at each winding to the phase magnitudes, so as to obtain the transformer admittance matrix \vec{Y} . This matrix links the primary and secondary voltages and currents, as expressed in (17) and derived from (16).

$$\vec{Y} = C_I^{-1} \cdot \vec{Y}_{\text{primitive}} \cdot C_U \tag{17}$$

The three-phase windings of power transformers may be connected in several ways. In high voltage transmission the most popular connections are star and delta, although the zig-zag connection is also used in distribution systems, depicted in Figure 14. Consequently, connectivity matrices must be computed for each configuration.

Figure 14: Zig-zag transformer connection

3.2.1 Delta-star (Dy) connection

Figure 15 shows the three-phase delta-star (Dy) connection.

Figure 15: Delta - star connection

The transformation matrix C_U , which relates the voltages of each winding to the corresponding phase voltages, is given explicitly in (18) and in compact form in (19).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{U}_1 \\ \vec{U}_2 \\ \vec{U}_3 \\ \vec{U}_4 \\ \vec{U}_5 \\ \vec{U}_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{U}_A \\ \vec{U}_B \\ \vec{U}_C \\ \vec{U}_a \\ \vec{U}_b \\ \vec{U}_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

$$\vec{U}_{\text{coils}} = C_U \cdot \vec{U}_{\text{phases}} \quad (19)$$

Similarly, the inverse current connectivity matrix C_I^{-1} is obtained as shown in (20) and in compact form in (21).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_A \\ \vec{I}_B \\ \vec{I}_C \\ \vec{I}_a \\ \vec{I}_b \\ \vec{I}_c \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_1 \\ \vec{I}_2 \\ \vec{I}_3 \\ \vec{I}_4 \\ \vec{I}_5 \\ \vec{I}_6 \end{bmatrix} \quad (20)$$

$$\vec{I}_{\text{phases}} = C_I^{-1} \cdot \vec{I}_{\text{coils}} \quad (21)$$

The full transformer admittance matrix for the Dy connection is shown in (23) and it is obtained by substituting the connectivity matrices (18) and (20) into (22).

$$\vec{Y} = C_I^{-1} \cdot \vec{Y}_{\text{primitive}} \cdot C_U \quad (22)$$

All nine possible three-phase transformer connection configurations, combining star, delta, and zigzag, have been detailed in the master thesis of Alex Blanco [24]. For a more in-depth explanation of the three-phase modelling of transformers, as well as of the other components, the reader is kindly referred to that document.

$$\vec{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2\vec{Y}_s + \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & -\frac{\vec{Y}_s - \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & -\frac{\vec{Y}_s - \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}^*m_fm_t} & 0 & \frac{\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}^*m_fm_t} \\ -\frac{\vec{Y}_s - \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & \frac{2\vec{Y}_s + \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & -\frac{\vec{Y}_s - \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & \frac{\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}^*m_fm_t} & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}^*m_fm_t} & 0 \\ -\frac{\vec{Y}_s - \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & -\frac{\vec{Y}_s - \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & \frac{2\vec{Y}_s + \vec{Y}_{sh}}{3m^2m_f^2} & 0 & \frac{\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}^*m_fm_t} & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}^*m_fm_t} \\ \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}m_tm_f} & \frac{\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}m_tm_f} & 0 & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m_t^2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}m_tm_f} & \frac{\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}m_tm_f} & 0 & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m_t^2} & 0 \\ \frac{\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}m_tm_f} & 0 & \frac{-\vec{Y}_s}{\sqrt{3}\vec{m}m_tm_f} & 0 & 0 & \frac{\vec{Y}_s + \frac{\vec{Y}_{sh}}{2}}{m_t^2} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

3.3 Loads

Owing to the large number and diversity of loads present in power networks, it is preferable to group loads and treat them as bulk consumption points, rather than employing distinct models for rotating, static, and converter-based loads [25]. The model used for the loads is the ZIP model, meaning it is considered as a combination of impedance, current, and power loads, as depicted in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Schematic ZIP load model

In steady-state applications, most system loads can be effectively represented as three-phase power sinks, connected either in star or delta configuration depending on system requirements [23]. Figure 17 illustrates a star-connected load with the neutral point solidly grounded, alongside a delta-connected load. As will be shown later, the power flow formulation operates using phase-to-neutral voltages and line currents, since the per-unit normalization is based on these quantities. For this reason, the developed tool models all loads as star-connected. Consequently, a preliminary conversion is required for delta-connected loads. The software must therefore be capable of transforming impedance, current, and power from delta to star equivalents.

Figure 17: Star-connected load (left) and delta-connected load (right) representations

3.3.1 Impedance (\mathbf{Z}) definition

Three-phase loads defined as constant impedance can be connected either in star or delta configurations. If the impedance load is defined in star, the diagonal of the 3x3 matrix shown in (24), is simply filled with these values.

$$\vec{Y}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Y}_a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \vec{Y}_b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \vec{Y}_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

However, if the load is defined in delta connection, the 3x3 matrix shown of (25) will be used to mathematically represent the load.

$$\vec{Y}_0 = \frac{1}{3} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Y}_{ab} + \vec{Y}_{ca} & -\vec{Y}_{ab} & -\vec{Y}_{ca} \\ -\vec{Y}_{ab} & \vec{Y}_{ab} + \vec{Y}_{bc} & -\vec{Y}_{bc} \\ -\vec{Y}_{ca} & -\vec{Y}_{bc} & \vec{Y}_{bc} + \vec{Y}_{ca} \end{bmatrix} \quad (25)$$

These matrices are also applicable for other shunt elements like capacitor banks.

3.3.2 Current (\mathbf{I}) definition

Traditionally, in positive sequence power flow analysis, constant current loads are directly stored in the \vec{I}_0 vector. However, since we are performing a three-phase power flow, the voltage angles of phases b and c are not zero, so it must be taken into account for both star (26) and delta-connected (27) current loads.

$$\vec{I}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_a^* e^{j\delta_a} \\ \vec{I}_b^* e^{j\delta_b} \\ \vec{I}_c^* e^{j\delta_c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

$$\vec{I}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\vec{I}_{ab}^* e^{j(\delta_a - \delta_b)} - \vec{I}_{ca}^* e^{j(\delta_c - \delta_a)}}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \frac{\vec{I}_{bc}^* e^{j(\delta_b - \delta_c)} - \vec{I}_{ab}^* e^{j(\delta_a - \delta_b)}}{\sqrt{3}} \\ \frac{\vec{I}_{ca}^* e^{j(\delta_c - \delta_a)} - \vec{I}_{bc}^* e^{j(\delta_b - \delta_c)}}{\sqrt{3}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

3.3.3 Power (P) definition

Finally, if the load is defined as constant power, the values are stored in the \vec{S}_0 vector for star loads (28), while the corresponding delta-to-star transformation must be applied (29). Note that the founded transformation also involves the voltage, here the complete phasor. In both cases, the power and current transformation vector to star, will be updated in each iteration, adding significant complexity compared to the traditional power flow.

$$\vec{S}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{S}_a \\ \vec{S}_b \\ \vec{S}_c \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

$$\vec{S}_0 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\vec{U}_a \cdot \vec{S}_{ab}}{\vec{U}_a - \vec{U}_b} - \frac{\vec{U}_a \cdot \vec{S}_{ca}}{\vec{U}_c - \vec{U}_a} \\ \frac{\vec{U}_b \cdot \vec{S}_{bc}}{\vec{U}_b - \vec{U}_c} - \frac{\vec{U}_b \cdot \vec{S}_{ab}}{\vec{U}_a - \vec{U}_b} \\ \frac{\vec{U}_c \cdot \vec{S}_{ca}}{\vec{U}_c - \vec{U}_a} - \frac{\vec{U}_c \cdot \vec{S}_{bc}}{\vec{U}_b - \vec{U}_c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

Note that only three-phase load models have been detailed in this deliverable. For a more in-depth explanation for three-phase but also for two-phase and single-phase load models, the reader is kindly referred to the master thesis of Alex Blanco [24].

3.4 Generators

For the power flow simulations, generators had been modelled as simple power injections into the system, which was completely valid. However, this is not sufficient when performing the short-circuit analysis, as the impedance of the generator must also be taken into account. VeraGrid has been programmed to accept a 3×3 impedance matrix, which includes both the self-impedances and the couplings between the *abc* phases. Furthermore, as this three-phase analysis is still under development, it is common to encounter generator impedances in the sequence domain. Therefore, Fortescue's theorem must be applied to obtain the equivalent values for the three phases:

$$\vec{Z}_{gen_{abc}} = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{Z}_1 + \vec{Z}_2 & \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{a}\vec{Z}_1 + \vec{a}^2\vec{Z}_2 & \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{a}^2\vec{Z}_1 + \vec{a}\vec{Z}_2 \\ \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{a}^2\vec{Z}_1 + \vec{a}\vec{Z}_2 & \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{Z}_1 + \vec{Z}_2 & \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{a}\vec{Z}_1 + \vec{a}^2\vec{Z}_2 \\ \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{a}\vec{Z}_1 + \vec{a}^2\vec{Z}_2 & \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{a}^2\vec{Z}_1 + \vec{a}\vec{Z}_2 & \vec{Z}_0 + \vec{Z}_1 + \vec{Z}_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

Where the transformation eigenvector $\vec{a} = e^{j2\pi/3}$ is used.

A key parameter that must be transferred from the power flow to the short-circuit analysis is the induced electromotive force (EMF) in the generators \vec{E} , as this is the only voltage that will not change during the fault. The electromotive force depends on the flux induced in the machine's rotor, and therefore on the excitation current. It can be assumed that the internal voltage \vec{E} of the generator remains constant during the duration of the fault.

The generator could be modelled during the short-circuit using the classic Thévenin equivalent, that is, as an ideal voltage source in series with the generator's impedance, as shown in the electrical circuit of Figure 18.

Figure 18: Thévenin equivalent circuit scheme

This circuit allows us to obtain the value of the induced electromotive force, given the voltage \vec{U}_{pf} and power \vec{S}_{pf} before the fault at the generator's output bus:

$$\vec{E} = \vec{U}_{pf} + \vec{Z}_{gen} \cdot \vec{I}_{pf} = \vec{U}_{pf} + \frac{\vec{S}_{pf}^*}{\vec{Y}_{gen} \cdot \vec{U}_{pf}^*} \quad (31)$$

However, this would require adding an additional bus to the original system between the generator's impedance and the ideal voltage source. Therefore, the generator is modelled using its Norton equivalent, that is, an ideal current source in parallel with the generator's impedance, as shown in the schematic of Figure 19. The Norton current source will take the value of the internal voltage multiplied by its admittance:

$$\vec{I}_N = \vec{Y}_{gen} \cdot \vec{E} \quad (32)$$

Figure 19: Norton equivalent circuit scheme

3.5 Voltage Source Converters

Voltage Source Converters (VSCs) have emerged as prevalent devices in modern power systems, playing a pivotal role in the integration of renewable energy sources, energy storage systems, and HVDC links, to name a few. VSCs are power electronics-based devices built with a set of semiconductors that when properly controlled allow the adjustment of electrical magnitudes. VSCs interface DC systems with AC systems as depicted in Figure 20. More complicated configurations can exist, some involving the neutral, yet they are discarded for this project and assumed this is a three-wire VSC on the AC as common with transmission systems.

Figure 20: Representation of a VSC

VSCs offer two degrees of controllability when seen from a steady-state perspective. Internally, they synthesize voltages so that these reference magnitudes are met. This typically involves controlling active and reactive powers, voltage magnitudes in the DC or AC side, or even angle/frequency on the AC side in the case of grid-forming converters [26]. Under normal conditions VSCs can regulate a given set of magnitudes, as captured in Table 1 (excluding droops and abnormal cross-combinations of controls).

Table 1: Non-exhaustive list of control combinations for a VSC under balanced conditions

Type	Control 1	Control 2
$P_t Q_t$	$P_{t,a} + P_{t,b} + P_{t,c}$	$Q_{t,a} + Q_{t,b} + Q_{t,c}$
$P_t U_t$	$P_{t,a} + P_{t,b} + P_{t,c}$	$U_{t,a}, U_{t,b}, U_{t,c}$
$P_t U_f$	$P_{t,a} + P_{t,b} + P_{t,c}$	$U_{f,p} - U_{f,n}$
$P_f Q_t$	$P_{f,p} + P_{f,n}$	$Q_{t,a} + Q_{t,b} + Q_{t,c}$
$P_f U_t$	$P_{f,p} + P_{f,n}$	$U_{t,a}, U_{t,b}, U_{t,c}$
$P_f U_f$	$P_{f,p} + P_{f,n}$	$U_{f,p} - U_{f,n}$
$U_t \delta_t$	$U_{t,a}, U_{t,b}, U_{t,c}$	$\delta_{t,a}, \delta_{t,b}, \delta_{t,c}$

Table 1 showcases some of the anticipated controls for systems under balanced conditions. In these cases, the powers on the three phases would be the same, voltages magnitudes take the same values, and angles maintain a perfect 120 degree shift between them. However, under unbalanced conditions, the situation changes considerably. There is little point in controlling the sum of powers, as large unbalances can take place, potentially forcing VSCs to saturate some of phases so as to not surpass its current limits. Hence, it is conventionally proposed to control powers and voltages in the positive sequence as described in [27].

During short-circuit conditions, and depending on the grid codes and priorities of the grid operator, it is proposed to inject current in the negative sequence to minimize the negative sequence voltages, while keeping some current margin in the positive sequence to boost the positive sequence voltage [28]. The grid-support converters can provide is dependent upon the maximum current its internal semiconductors can stand. Compared to synchronous generators, VSCs have a much more limited current provision, often in the range 1.0 to 2.0 p.u., which is several orders of magnitude smaller in comparison to traditional generators. The inclusion of VSCs into the power flow and short-circuit formulation must ensure the following limits are met at all times:

$$I_{t,a} \leq I_{\max}, \quad (33)$$

$$I_{t,b} \leq I_{\max}, \quad (34)$$

$$I_{t,c} \leq I_{\max}, \quad (35)$$

where I_{\max} is the upper limit current magnitude a converter can admit, as specified by the manufacturer, and currents of the form $I_{t,x}$, where x would symbolize one of the three phases, can be extracted from the powers and voltages depicted in Figure 20 through:

$$I_{t,x} = \frac{\sqrt{P_{t,x}^2 + Q_{t,x}^2}}{U_{t,x}}. \quad (36)$$

Following grid codes, as the specification of currents is given in the sequences, the

Fortescue transformation has to be applied:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_{t,a} \\ \vec{I}_{t,b} \\ \vec{I}_{t,c} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & \vec{a}^2 & \vec{a} \\ 1 & \vec{a} & \vec{a}^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{I}_{t,0} \\ \vec{I}_{t,1} \\ \vec{I}_{t,2} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (37)$$

where the current $\vec{I}_{t,0}$ becomes zero in a three-wire AC system and the currents $\vec{I}_{t,1}$ and $\vec{I}_{t,2}$ are commonly a function of the voltage drop.

Traditional power system analysis for faults and power flows relies on symmetrical components. This method is effective because the sequences are decoupled in conventional networks, allowing the system's state to be solved by superimposing the results from each sequence. However, this paradigm breaks down with power electronic converters, as their operational limits, particularly current magnitude, exist in the physical abc domain. One must first synthesize the total current in each phase from all three sequences to determine if a limit is violated.

Mapping the dynamic behavior of grid-following or grid-forming converters into a steady-state model is also fraught with difficulty. The analysis must account not only for current limits but also for control priorities between active and reactive power, compliance with intricate grid codes, and discrete control actions, such as fault-ride-through logic, which alter the converter's operating state during a disturbance. Consequently, accurately modeling converter behavior for system studies remains a significant and largely unsolved challenge, marking it as a critical area for ongoing research.

- A substation transformer between the external grid and the slack bus 650, and a distribution transformer between buses 633 and 634.
- Multiple balanced and unbalanced loads modelled as constant impedance (Z), constant power (P), and constant current (I), with three-phase connections in star (Y) and delta (D), connections between two phases, and also between one phase and the ground.
- Shunt capacitor banks for reactive power compensation, also with different phasing configurations (three-phase and single-phase).

The base voltage levels of the system are 115 kV on the transmission side and 4,16 kV on the distribution side, with a downstream low-voltage level of 0,48 kV at bus 634. The total nominal load is around 3,8 MVA, distributed across residential, commercial, and industrial consumers.

Due to the network's unbalanced and mixed-phase nature, this test feeder is widely recognised as a challenging yet representative case for validating unbalanced power flow solvers. The parameters used for the modelling and calculation of the transformers are presented in Table 2, for the loads in Table 3, for the lines in Table 4, and finally for the capacitor banks in Table 5. The impedance and admittance matrices for each line configuration are shown in the main author's master thesis [24].

Table 2: Transformer data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case

From Bus	To Bus	U_{HV} [kV]	U_{LV} [kV]	Conn.	S_r [kVA]	R [%]	X [%]
Grid	650	115	4,16	Dy5	5 000	1	8
633	634	4,16	0,48	Yy0	500	1,1	2

Table 3: Load data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case

Bus	Mod.	P_a [kW]	Q_a [kVAr]	P_b [kW]	Q_b [kVAr]	P_c [kW]	Q_c [kVAr]
634	P - Y	160	110	120	90	120	90
645	P - Y	0	0	170	125	0	0
646	Z - D	0	0	230	132	0	0
652	Z - Y	128	86	0	0	0	0
671	P - D	385	220	385	220	385	220
675	P - Y	485	190	68	60	290	212
692	I - D	0	0	0	0	170	151
611	I - Y	0	0	0	0	170	80
632/671	P - Y	17	10	66	38	117	68
Total		1175	616	1039	665	1252	821

Table 4: Line data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case

From Bus	To Bus	Length [ft.]	Configuration	Phasing
632	645	500	3	B C
632	633	500	2	A B C
645	646	300	3	B C
650	632	2000	1	A B C
684	652	800	7	A
632	671	2000	1	A B C
671	684	300	4	A C
671	680	1000	1	A B C
671	692	-	Switch	A B C
684	611	300	5	C
692	675	500	6	A B C

Table 5: Capacitor bank data of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case

Bus	Q _a [kVAr]	Q _b [kVAr]	Q _c [kVAr]
675	200	200	200
611	-	-	100
Total	200	200	300

The following comparison contrasts the magnitude and angle of voltages obtained using the VeraGrid's developed simulation tool with those provided as reference data by the IEEE [31]. Voltage magnitude and angle results are shown for phase a in Table 6 and plotted in Figures 22 and 23, respectively. The values are perfectly matched.

Table 6: Phase a Voltage Profile of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case

Bus	Reference Data		VeraGrid Simulation	
	U_a [p.u.]	δ_a [°]	U_a [p.u.]	δ_a [°]
650	1,0625	0,00	1,0625	0,00
632	1,0210	-2,49	1,0210	-2,49
645	-	-	-	-
646	-	-	-	-
633	1,0180	-2,56	1,0180	-2,55
634	0,9940	-3,23	0,9940	-3,23
671	0,9900	-5,30	0,9900	-5,30
684	0,9881	-5,32	0,9881	-5,32
611	-	-	-	-
692	0,9900	-5,30	0,9900	-5,30
675	0,9835	-5,56	0,9835	-5,55
680	0,9900	-5,30	0,9900	-5,30
652	0,9825	-5,25	0,9825	-5,25

Figure 22: Voltage magnitude per bus in phase a

Figure 23: Voltage angle per bus in phase a

This time, the obtained values of magnitude and angle of the phase b voltage along all the buses also correspond perfectly with the reference, as can be seen in Table 7 and in the graphs in Figures 24 and 25, respectively.

Table 7: Phase b Voltage Profile of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case

Bus	Reference Data		VeraGrid Simulation	
	U_b [p.u.]	δ_b [°]	U_b [p.u.]	δ_b [°]
650	1,0500	-120,00	1,0500	-120,00
632	1,0420	-121,72	1,0420	-121,72
645	1,0329	-121,90	1,0328	-121,90
646	1,0311	-121,98	1,0311	-121,98
633	1,0401	-121,77	1,0401	-121,77
634	1,0218	-122,22	1,0218	-122,22
671	1,0529	-122,34	1,0529	-122,34
684	-	-	-	-
611	-	-	-	-
692	1,0529	-122,34	1,0529	-122,34
675	1,0553	-122,52	1,0553	-122,52
680	1,0529	-122,34	1,0529	-122,34
652	-	-	-	-

Figure 24: Voltage magnitude per bus in phase b

Figure 25: Voltage angle per bus in phase b

Finally, Table 8 and Figures 26 and 27 compare the magnitude and angle of the phase c voltage, respectively. Again, the results simulated by VeraGrid correspond to the reference values, thus validating the implemented three-phase grid modelling and power flow formulation.

Table 8: Phase c Voltage Profile of the IEEE 13-bus Test Case

Bus	Reference Data		VeraGrid Simulation	
	U_c [p.u.]	δ_c [°]	U_c [p.u.]	δ_c [°]
650	1,0687	120,00	1,0687	120,00
632	1,0174	117,83	1,0174	117,83
645	1,0155	117,86	1,0154	117,86
646	1,0134	117,90	1,0134	117,90
633	1,0148	117,82	1,0148	117,83
634	0,9960	117,34	0,9960	117,35
671	0,9778	116,02	0,9777	116,03
684	0,9758	115,92	0,9757	115,93
611	0,9738	115,78	0,9737	115,78
692	0,9770	116,02	0,9777	116,03
675	0,9758	116,03	0,9758	116,04
680	0,9778	116,02	0,9777	116,03
652	-	-	-	-

Figure 26: Voltage magnitude per bus in phase c

Figure 27: Voltage angle per bus in phase c

4.2 IEEE European Low Voltage Test Feeder

To validate the three-phase power flow formulation developed in VeraGrid, the IEEE European Low Voltage Test Feeder has been simulated. This benchmark was introduced by the IEEE PES Distribution Systems Analysis Subcommittee to support research in low-voltage distribution systems, particularly those commonly found in Europe [32]. It includes both static and time-series simulation results, making it suitable for comparison against custom implementations such as the one developed here by eRoots Analytics.

This large-scale test feeder, depicted in Figure 28, consists of a radial low-voltage system operating at 416 V (phase-to-phase) and 50 Hz, connected to the medium-voltage network through an 800 kVA transformer, and comprising 906 buses. The transformer features a delta-grounded wye configuration and steps voltage down from 11 kV to 0.416 kV. The medium-voltage system is modelled as an ideal voltage source with internal impedance defined by short-circuit current levels.

The feeder includes 905 distribution lines and 55 constant (P) loads connected across multiple phases. The lines are defined by their terminal buses, length and impedances per unit length. Loads are connected across individual phases and are uniformly rated at 1 kW with a power factor of 0.95. Each load is associated with a time-varying profile defined over a 24-hour period with one-minute resolution. A more detailed information of the parameters of this grid is provided in the master thesis of Alex Blanco [24].

Figure 28: Single-line diagram of the European Low Voltage Test Feeder

The benchmark also includes reference simulation results obtained using OpenDSS [33] and GridLAB-D [34], which serve as a basis for validating simulation tools and models. This test feeder was developed to address the growing need for dynamic simulations in the context of Volt-Var optimisation, integration of renewables and storage systems, and time-dependent control strategies [35].

After building the test network and simulating the three-phase power flow implemented in VeraGrid, the results obtained are compared with the reference data. Given the large volume of data, a couple of representative buses have been selected to illustrate the voltage evolution over time.

Figure 29 shows the voltage of phase *c* at bus 619 during hour 14, while Figure 30 displays the voltage of phase *b* at bus 900 during hour 5. This configuration has been chosen to highlight the voltage drop both at a mid-point of the radial network and at one of its end points. Moreover, the figures reflect data from different phases, different buses, and different time periods, thereby ensuring the robustness of the validation.

As with the American 13-bus case, the results obtained here also show excellent agreement in this European 906-bus case. Small discrepancies may be due to the fact that in this case the line impedance data was given in sequences, and in the conversion to abc some information may have been lost.

Figure 30: Phase b voltage profile comparison for hour 5

4.3 Single Line-to-Ground Fault (SLG)

The short-circuit calculation method will be tested using the 13-bus test network, which was already constructed for the power flow and whose results are exactly the same as the reference, thus fully validated. As shown in the schematic of Figure 31, a fault will be simulated on phase a to earth at bus 634 with two fault impedance values.

A generator has been added to bus 632, providing an equivalent power to the network to which the system was connected. The sequence impedance values for the generator are $Z_1 = 0.004 + 0.5j$ p.u. for the positive sequence, $Z_2 = 0.02 + 0.5j$ p.u. for the negative sequence, and $Z_0 = 0.01 + 0.08j$ p.u. for the zero sequence.

The fault admittance is defined by the user in VeraGrid, while its matrix depends on the fault type and the phases involved.

Figure 31: Phase-to-ground short-circuit at the bus 634 of the IEEE 13 Node Test Feeder

A single line-to-ground fault (SLG) occurs when one phase conductor accidentally makes contact with the ground. It is illustrated in Figure 32 for phase a, and the corresponding fault admittance matrix is given by:

$$\vec{Y}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Y}_f^a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{38}$$

Figure 32: Single Line-to-Ground Fault (SLG)

Figure 33: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a SLG fault

Figure 34: Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase b during a SLG fault

Figure 35: Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase c during a SLG fault

Figures 33–35 show the VeraGrid results for the voltage magnitudes across all buses during a single line-to-ground (SLG) fault. In phase a, the voltage collapses nearly to zero at the faulted bus (634) and drops significantly at the adjacent bus (633), with the severity increasing as the fault resistance decreases. In contrast, phases b and c experience a slight rise at the faulted location due to the local reference shift, while farther from the fault the dominant effect is the voltage drop caused by fault current flowing through the network impedances, leading to reduced voltages compared to the pre-fault condition [36].

4.4 Line-to-Line Fault (LL)

A line-to-line fault (LL) occurs when two phase conductors come into contact with each other. Figure 36 shows the fault between phases c and a, and the corresponding fault admittance matrix is given by:

$$\vec{Y}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Y}_f^{ca} & 0 & -\vec{Y}_f^{ca} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\vec{Y}_f^{ca} & 0 & \vec{Y}_f^{ca} \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Figure 36: Line-to-Line Fault (LL)

A line-to-line (LL) fault is simulated in VeraGrid between phases c and a at bus 634 of the IEEE 13-Node Test Feeder. Figures 37 and 39 show that both faulted phases undergo a strong voltage drop, with the relative severity depending on the fault resistance: phase a is more affected for $R_f = 1$ p.u., while phase c shows a deeper dip for $R_f = 0.1$ p.u. This difference reflects how the two phases share the fault current path and how the drop distributes with network impedance and R_f . In the surrounding buses the impact is still visible, but voltages gradually recover with distance from the fault.

Figure 38 presents the results for the healthy phase b, which remains nearly uniform but slightly reduced across the network. Unlike the SLG case, no voltage rise is observed in the healthy phase, since two phases are simultaneously pulled down and the neutral shift effect is suppressed.

Figure 37: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a LL fault

Figure 38: Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase b during a LL fault

Figure 39: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a LL fault

4.5 Double Line-to-Ground Fault (DLG)

A double line-to-ground fault (DLG) occurs when two phase conductors simultaneously make contact with the ground. Figure 40 illustrates the fault involving phases c and a , and the corresponding fault admittance matrix is given by:

$$\vec{Y}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Y}_f^a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \vec{Y}_f^c \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

Figure 40: Double Line-to-Ground Fault (DLG)

A double line-to-ground (DLG) fault is simulated in VeraGrid at bus 634 of the IEEE 13-Node Test Feeder, involving phases a and c connected to ground. Figures 41 and 43 show that both affected phases undergo a severe voltage collapse, almost reaching zero at the faulted bus, which represents a deeper drop than in the LL case where the voltages remained above 0.4 p.u. In the neighbouring buses the impact is still evident, while farther away the voltages gradually recover.

The behaviour of the healthy phase b , shown in Figure 42, is markedly different: a clear voltage rise appears at the buses closest to the fault (633 and 634). This occurs because the simultaneous grounding of two phases strongly distorts the local reference, displacing the neutral point and forcing the remaining phase upward. This contrasts with the LL fault, where no rise was observed and the healthy phase experienced a more uniform slight depression across the system [37].

Figure 41: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a DLG fault

Figure 42: Voltage magnitude per bus in the health phase b during a DLG fault

Figure 43: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a DLG fault

4.6 Three-Phase Fault (LLL)

A three-phase (LLL) fault occurs when all three phase conductors come into contact with each other. Figure 44 shows the fault between phases a , b , and c , and the corresponding fault admittance matrix is given by:

$$\vec{Y}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Y}_f^{ab} + \vec{Y}_f^{ca} & -\vec{Y}_f^{ab} & -\vec{Y}_f^{ca} \\ -\vec{Y}_f^{ab} & \vec{Y}_f^{ab} + \vec{Y}_f^{bc} & -\vec{Y}_f^{bc} \\ -\vec{Y}_f^{ca} & -\vec{Y}_f^{bc} & \vec{Y}_f^{bc} + \vec{Y}_f^{ca} \end{bmatrix} \quad (41)$$

Figure 44: Three-Phase Fault (LLL)

A three-phase (LLL) fault is simulated in VeraGrid at bus 634 of the IEEE 13-Node Test Feeder. Figures 45–47 show the voltage profiles of phases a , b , and c across the system during the disturbance. In this case, all three phases behave symmetrically, with the voltages collapsing almost to zero at the faulted bus and showing a marked drop at the upstream bus 633. The influence of the fault resistance is negligible, since the short circuit equally involves all phases. At the remaining buses, the voltages settle to nearly uniform values slightly below the pre-fault condition, reflecting the balanced nature of this type of fault.

Figure 45: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a LLL fault

Figure 46: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase b during a LLL fault

Figure 47: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a LLL fault

4.7 Three-Phase-to-Ground Fault (LLLG)

A three-phase-to-ground (LLLG) fault occurs when all three phase conductors come into simultaneous contact with the ground. Figure 48 illustrates the fault involving phases a, b, and c, and the corresponding fault admittance matrix is given by:

$$\vec{Y}_f = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{Y}_f^a & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \vec{Y}_f^b & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \vec{Y}_f^c \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

Figure 48: Three-Phase-to-Ground Fault (LLLG)

Finally, a three-phase-to-ground (LLLG) fault is simulated in VeraGrid at bus 634 of the IEEE 13-Node Test Feeder. Figures 49–51 show that all three phases decrease uniformly, collapsing close to zero at the faulted bus and exhibiting a marked drop at the upstream bus 633. The remaining buses present nearly uniform voltages slightly below the pre-fault condition, similar to the LLL case. The main difference is that the fault resistance plays a more significant role: for $R_f = 1$ p.u. the voltages at the faulted bus do not fall completely to zero, highlighting the stronger influence of grounding impedance in this type of fault. A detailed explanation of the three-phase power flow and short-circuit analysis implemented in VeraGrid can be found in the related master thesis [24].

Figure 49: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase a during a LLLG fault

Figure 50: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase b during a LLLG fault

Figure 51: Voltage magnitude per bus in the faulted phase c during a LLLG fault

5 Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the implementation of balanced and unbalanced systems for steady state analysis. The balanced steady state analysis is implemented in DIgSILENT PowerFactory while the three-phase unbalanced analysis is represented within the open-source VeraGrid environment, based on the methods and results developed in [24].

The balanced steady state analysis aims to evaluate the flexibility contribution from active demands, such as heat pumps, EVs and battery storage, in order to alleviate voltage variations and line congestions. An intelligent controller has been designed for dispatching of flexibility assets using DPL language. Three types of flexible loads are considered: PV generation and electrical storage, heat pumps and EV loads. Also the Thermonet concept can be included as a flexible load. The intelligent control of flexibility assets is initially validated in Hyllegaard Høje, a Danish Demonstration Site. A CEMS-Based Control Architecture developed by Neogrid is presented as a solution that integrates forecasting, optimization, and real-time control features to exploit the asset flexibility of an energy community.

Unbalance steady state models for power flow and short-circuit calculation are also presented. This will be later used to evaluate the impact of inverter-based components to the distribution grid in terms of voltage stability. An open source software environment, VeraGrid, is considered to make the models available and easy to adapt or extend for future research and development needs.

The work has demonstrated that the unbalanced three-phase power flow method converges reliably across different test networks, including standard IEEE feeders and more complex configurations. The results obtained with VeraGrid match closely those given from the IEEE and simulated with OpenDSS, PowerFactory or Matlab, confirming the soundness of the Newton-Raphson algorithm adapted for phase components. The tool successfully captures key phenomena associated with unbalanced systems and allows for the detailed observation of nodal voltages and branch power flows.

Similarly, the implemented short-circuit module is capable of simulating stationary conditions after a fault event for all relevant fault types in unbalanced distribution networks, single-phase, two-phase and three-phase faults with and without ground connection. The flexibility to define the fault admittance matrix directly permits the representation of realistic fault conditions, including the modelling of fault impedance. The validation examples show that voltage drops and fault current injections behave as expected, both in terms of physical interpretation and numerical results.

In summary, the developed frameworks in PowerFactory and VeraGrid are now prepared to support the rest of the tasks in FLEXDIS, offering robust and accurate capabilities balanced and unbalanced steady state analysis.

References

- [1] R. Aljarrah, H. Marzooghi, V. Terzija, and J. Yu, "Issues and challenges of steady-state fault calculation methods in power systems with a high penetration of non-synchronous generation," in *2019 IEEE Milan PowerTech*. Milan, Italy: IEEE, 2019, pp. 1–6.
- [2] J. Song, J. Fanals-Batllo, L. Marín, M. Cheah-Mane, E. Prieto-Araujo, E. Bullich-Massagué, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "A short-circuit calculation solver for power systems with power electronics converters," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 157, p. 109839, June 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0142061524000607>
- [3] M. Laughton, "System representation in phase frame of reference - analysis of unbalanced polyphase networks by the method of phase co-ordinates," *Proceedings of the IEE*, 1968.
- [4] Laughton, "Fault analysis of unbalanced polyphase networks by the method of phase co-ordinates," *Proceedings of the IEE*, 1969.
- [5] S. P. Vera, *VeraGrid - Power systems planning and simulation software*, <https://veragrid.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>, eRoots Analytics, 2025.
- [6] O. Elgerd, *Electric Energy Systems Theory: An Introduction*. Tata McGraw-Hill Publishing Company Limited, 1983.
- [7] E. Csanyi, "The structure of electric power systems: Energy generation, distribution and transmission," *Electrical Engineering Portal*, 2025.
- [8] M. A. Shlash, "Three-phase analysis of unbalanced power system networks," Ph.D. dissertation, Department of Electrical Engineering and Electronics, University of Manchester Institute of Science and Technology, Manchester, UK, 1974.
- [9] M. H. Hesse and J. Sabath, "Ehv double-circuit untransposed transmission line-analysis and tests," *IEEE Transactions on Power Apparatus and Systems*, 1971.
- [10] R. Wasley and M. Shlash, "Newton-raphson algorithm for 3-phase load flow," *Proceedings of the Institution of Electrical Engineers*, 1974.
- [11] B. Harker and J. Arrillaga, "Three-phase ac/dc load flow," *Proceedings of the Institution of Electrical Engineers*, 1979.
- [12] P. M. Anderson, *Analysis of Faulted Power Systems*. Iowa State University Press, 1973.

- [13] E. Acha and M. Madrigal, *Power System Harmonics: Computer Modelling and Analysis*. John Wiley & Sons, 2001.
- [14] J. I. Candela, "Transmission of electrical energy: High voltage power lines," polytechnical University of Catalonia.
- [15] J. R. Carson, "Wave propagation in overhead wires with ground return," *Bell System Technical Journal*, vol. 5, no. 4, pp. 539–554, 1926.
- [16] H. W. Dommel, *Electro-Magnetic Transients Program (EMTP) Theory Book*. Bonneville, 1986.
- [17] DIgSILENT GmbH, "PowerFactory – Power System Analysis Software," Gomaringen, Germany, 2024, software. [Online]. Available: <https://www.digsilent.de/en/powerfactory.html>
- [18] E. Acha, *FACTS : modelling and simulation in power networks*. John Wiley and Sons, 2004.
- [19] John J. Grainger and William D. Stevenson, Jr., *Power System Analysis*,. McGraw-Hill, 1994.
- [20] E. Acha, *Three-phase Power Flow Analysis*. Coimbra, 2015.
- [21] A. Blanco and J. I. Candela, "Study and design of protection current transformers," Bachelor's Thesis, UPC, Terrassa, Spain, 2024.
- [22] P. Barker and R. Smith, *Transformers: Principles and Applications*. Wiley-IEEE Press, 2001.
- [23] M. Chen and W. Dillon, "Power system modeling," *Proceedings of the IEE 62*, pp. 901–915, 1974.
- [24] A. Blanco-Castro, "Modelling and analysis of three-phase unbalanced electric power systems," Master's Thesis, UPC, Barcelona, Spain, 2025.
- [25] B. M. Weedy, B. J. Cory, N. Jenkins, J. B. Ekanayake, and G. Strbac, *Electric power systems*. John Wiley & Sons, 2012.
- [26] J. Song, J. Fanals-Batlloiri, L. Marín, M. Cheah-Mane, E. Prieto-Araujo, E. Bullich-Massagué, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "A short-circuit calculation solver for power systems with power electronics converters," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 157, p. 109839, 2024.

- [27] J. Song, M. Cheah-Mane, E. Prieto-Araujo, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Short-circuit calculation of power systems with power electronics converters considering asymmetrical faults and converter limits," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 170, p. 110804, 2025.
- [28] J. Fanals-Batllo, J. Song, M. Cheah-Mañé, E. Prieto-Araujo, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Grid code analysis considering converter-based grid voltage support during faults," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 148, p. 109000, 2023.
- [29] IEEE Distribution System Analysis Subcommittee, "IEEE 13 Node Test Feeder," 2004, the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers, Inc.
- [30] IEEE PES Distribution System Analysis Subcommittee, "IEEE PES Test Feeders – Resources," <https://cmte.ieee.org/pes-testfeeders/resources/>, 2025.
- [31] K. P. Schneider, B. A. Mather, B. C. Pal, C. W. Ten, G. J. Shirek, H. Zhu, J. C. Fuller, J. L. R. Pereira, L. F. Ochoa, L. R. de Araujo, R. C. Dugan, S. Matthias, S. Paudyal, T. E. McDermott, and W. Kersting, "Analytic considerations and design basis for the IEEE distribution test feeders," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. PP, no. 99, pp. 1–1, 2017.
- [32] IEEE PES Distribution Systems Analysis Subcommittee, "IEEE PES Distribution System Radial Test Feeders," <http://ewh.ieee.org/soc/pes/dsacom/testfeeders.html>, 2004.
- [33] Electric Power Research Institute, "OpenDSS: Distribution System Simulator," <http://sourceforge.net/projects/electricdss/>, 2025.
- [34] U.S. Department of Energy, Pacific Northwest National Laboratory, "GridLAB-D: Power Distribution Simulation Software," <http://www.gridlabd.org/>, 2025.
- [35] R. C. Dugan, W. H. Kersting, S. Carneiro, R. F. Arritt, and T. E. McDermott, "Roadmap for the IEEE PES test feeders," in *2009 IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting*, 2009.
- [36] J. Arrillaga and N. Watson, *Power System Electromagnetic Transients Simulation*. IEE Power Energy Series, 2003.
- [37] P. Kundur, *Power System Stability and Control*. McGraw-Hill, 1994.

**Funded by
the European Union**